

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Playback attracts prospecting individuals, but habitat quality is key for settlement in the Wryneck *Jynx torquilla*

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Abstract

1. Organisms do not only use personal but also social information for habitat selection. However, the use and relative importance of these two sources of information for settlement decisions remain unclear for many species. Conservation tools that attract target species to available or restored habitat rely on social information, while additional or interacting effects of personal information may limit their efficiency.
2. Here, we investigated the effects of food availability (individually acquired personal information) and conspecific vocalization (social information) on habitat selection of a regionally endangered, migrating woodpecker, the Wryneck *Jynx torquilla*. First, we analysed the species' occurrence in relation to food availability and habitat characteristics in general. Then, we conducted a playback experiment, during both the prospecting period and the breeding period, in previously unoccupied plots with different conditions of food availability to disentangle the relative importance of food availability and conspecific vocalization for habitat selection during both the prospecting period and the breeding period.
3. Wryneck occurrence increased with food availability (i.e. ant nest density) and slightly related to food accessibility (i.e. the proportion of bare ground). Food availability varied considerably among habitat types, with the highest values in vineyards and the lowest values in intensively managed grasslands. Within the experimental framework, high food availability increased the probability of both Wryneck prospecting and breeding. In turn, playback had a positive effect on Wryneck prospecting under poor but not favourable food conditions, but not on Wryneck breeding. Finally, playback did not exert a significant effect on breeding success.
4. *Practical implication:* Both personal and social information seem to affect Wryneck habitat selection behaviour. However, food availability as individually acquired personal information of a habitat cue mainly influenced Wryneck settlement decisions that led to breeding. Consequently, playback as social information through a simulated conspecific social cue is a potentially useful tool for Wryneck

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conservation, and the risk of attracting Wrynecks into an ecological trap is minimal. Nevertheless, habitat quality, and in particular food availability, are more important and a crucial requirements for successful conservation management.

KEYWORDS

ant nest density, conservation management, conspecific attraction, habitat selection, personal information, playback, social information

1 | INTRODUCTION

While habitat loss is a main driver of species decline worldwide (Foley et al., 2005), existing patches of suitable habitat often remain unoccupied, particularly after habitat restoration, implementation of compensatory measures, or following bottlenecks due to other threats (Palmer et al., 1997; Pulliam, 2000). However, attracting target species to unoccupied or restored suitable habitats remains challenging because mechanisms underlying habitat selection and settlement decisions are still unclear (Smith & Peacock, 1990; Valente et al., 2021).

Conspecific attraction is a common consequence of a species using social information to assess habitat quality, thereby reducing search and settlement costs (Danchin et al., 2004; Doligez et al., 2002; Stamps, 1988). The attraction to conspecifics and the tendency to preferentially settle near them evolve when social information is reliable and exists across many taxa (Buxton et al., 2020; Reed & Dobson, 1993). The phenomenon of conspecific attraction can also be used for designing effective conservation measures to influence the recolonization of unoccupied suitable habitats, as it allows for both a direct manipulation of individuals during habitat selection and a rapid response (Ahlering et al., 2010; Buxton et al., 2020; Stamps, 2001; Valente et al., 2021). While a number of studies have shown that influencing habitat selection by simulating conspecific presence can positively affect settlement decisions, most of them have focused exclusively on presence-absence responses (Valente et al., 2021). Thus, despite over 25 years of investigation into the use of conspecific attraction for conservation and management of birds, the fitness consequences of manipulating habitat selection by methods using the phenomenon of conspecific attraction remain poorly understood (Ahlering et al., 2010; Buxton et al., 2020; Valente et al., 2021).

Habitat selection often uses personal information about habitats and their quality, but social cues can also provide decisive information (Doligez et al., 2002; Doligez & Boulinier, 2008). Only in recent years have underlying mechanisms resulting in habitat selection decisions been increasingly investigated. These studies provide evidence that birds combine information on habitat quantity and quality and social cues for habitat selection (Rushing et al., 2021; Swift et al., 2023). Indeed, personal information interacts with acquired social information and jointly influences settlement decisions (Betts et al., 2008; Pärt et al., 2011). This interaction

results in a gradient of possible outcomes between two extremes, depending on whether personal or social cues have a greater impact. On the one hand, if personal information outweighs social information, the presence of conspecifics is expected to have less impact in habitats of lower quality (Danchin et al., 2004; Parejo et al., 2007). Individuals might be attracted to low quality habitat patches by neighbouring individuals, but after prospecting, they continue to search for a suitable habitat. On the other hand, if social information outweighs personal information, the presence of conspecifics can create ecological traps by providing preferred social cues in suboptimal habitats (Farrell et al., 2012; Nocera et al., 2006). This may result in a reduction in breeding success or survival. Although the efficacy of methods that use conspecific attraction to colonise unoccupied habitats depends strongly on these outcomes, little is known about the interaction between conspecific attraction (social information) and habitat quality (personal information).

Compared to other animals, vocalization plays a unique role in birds (Catchpole & Slater, 2008). Playback of vocalizations as a manipulation method simulating the presence of conspecifics is therefore of special interest in birds and has been used more often than decoys or other attraction methods (Ahlering et al., 2010; Buxton et al., 2020; Valente et al., 2021). Attraction to conspecific playback has repeatedly been detected in colonial waterbirds and territorial passerines (e.g. Burger, 1988; Ward & Schlossberg, 2004). However, few studies have looked beyond these two taxa, and their results remain inconclusive (Buxton et al., 2020; Valente et al., 2021).

Here, we investigated the response of the Eurasian Wryneck *Jynx torquilla* (hereafter 'Wryneck') to experimentally simulated vocalizations of conspecifics (social information) in relation to differential habitat quality (personal information). This small woodpecker species is generally limited by the availability of food resources (i.e. ants, Mermod et al., 2009) and breeding cavities (Coudrain et al., 2010). Wrynecks show five out of eight known indications for the existence of conspecific attraction in habitat selection (Ahlering et al., 2010): aggregated territories/patchy distributions, migratory behaviour, low survival, short breeding season, and asynchronous breeding (Glutz von Blotzheim, 1994; Tenan et al., 2021; van Wijk et al., 2013; Zwahlen & Schaub, 2024). Indeed, conspecific presence has been shown to increase territory colonization and has a strong positive influence on territory occupancy in Wrynecks (Mermod et al., 2009; Zingg et al., 2010).

The Wryneck is therefore an ideal study system to test the effect of an experimentally simulated social cue in situations with varying personal information.

In a two-step approach, we studied the interactions of playback, an experimentally simulated social cue, and habitat quality, a cue acquired by personal information, on prospecting and breeding in Wrynecks. First, we investigated whether food availability (i.e. ant nest density) as a proxy for habitat quality promoted Wryneck occurrence. Second, we tested whether Wrynecks showed higher prospecting and breeding probability on experimental plots with playback than on control plots without playback, and whether the experimental effect interacted with food availability. The results of this study will provide insights into the interactions between social and personal cues on settlement decisions and allow for recommendations to use playback as an effective (i.e. not resulting in ecological traps) and efficient tool for species conservation in general and for Wryneck conservation in particular (Ockendon et al., 2021; Valente et al., 2021).

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study species

The Wryneck is near threatened in Switzerland and a priority species of the Swiss Species Recovery Program (Knaus et al., 2021; Spaar & Ayé, 2016). Following a decline during the second half of the 20th century due to the loss of structural diversity caused by agricultural intensification in Switzerland, the Wryneck has recently colonized new habitats, such as vineyards and orchards (Knaus et al., 2018; Weisshaupt et al., 2011). The Wryneck is a secondary cavity breeder and feeds almost exclusively on ground-dwelling ants (Coudrain et al., 2010; Freitag, 1998; Mermod et al., 2009). In the absence of naturally occurring cavities, Wrynecks accept suitable nest boxes and even holes in artificial material, such as artificial pipe beam ends (Assandri et al., 2018; Zingg et al., 2010). After wintering on the Iberian Peninsula and in northwestern Africa (van Wijk et al., 2013), individuals arrive in Switzerland between mid-March and the beginning of April to raise one or, to a certain extent, two broods until July (Glutz von Blotzheim, 1994; Pauli, 2022; Tolkmitt et al., 2009). Site fidelity in Wrynecks has not yet been sufficiently quantified (Pauli, 2022; Tenan et al., 2021; Zwahlen & Schaub, 2024). However, a low apparent survival rate and high immigration rates suggest local recruitment and considerable emigration of juveniles from the natal population (Schaub et al., 2012; Tenan et al., 2021). Individual Wryneck home ranges in Switzerland vary from 2.1 to 9.2 ha (mean \pm standard deviation = 4.8 ± 2.4 ha, Weisshaupt et al., 2011).

2.2 | Study area and environmental data

Our study area extended over ca. 100 km along the southern foothills of the Swiss Jura Mountains (hereafter 'southern Jura

foothills'). The southern Jura foothills are characterized by structured habitats such as vineyards, extensive meadows, pastures, forests, and settlements, while their surroundings are dominated by intensive agriculture. It was a regular breeding ground for the Wryneck in the 20th century but breeding only occurred sporadically and at low densities in the central and largest part of the study area in the years before our study. While two Wryneck populations with more than 15 breeding pairs each have been re-established at the western and eastern ends of the study area over the last 20 years (Knaus et al., 2018; Pauli, 2022), the central and largest part of the study area remains unoccupied, despite the presence of suitable Wryneck habitat and numerous nest boxes within it. To test whether social attraction could be used to support colonization of this central area and thereby re-connect the existing breeding areas, we established 48 circular plots (hereafter referred to as 'experimental plots', Figure 1) with a radius of 125 m. They corresponded to the telemetry-derived 4.8 ha home-range of Wrynecks in Switzerland (Weisshaupt et al., 2011), while smaller, observation-derived territory sizes have been reported from northern Italy (Assandri et al., 2018). No Wrynecks bred on the 48 experimental plots in the 2 years prior to our study, and only four of these experimental plots, or 8%, had been occupied in the 4 years prior to our study (the average lifespan of a Wryneck should not exceed 4 years; BirdLife International, 2024; Tenan et al., 2021). We assigned each plot to one of three main habitat categories depending on the predominant land use (meadow: $n=20$ plots, pasture: $n=16$ plots, or vineyard: $n=12$ plots). Experimental plots were equipped with a total of 221 nest boxes, which have been installed since 2016 for Wryneck conservation. The number of nest boxes available on each plot varied from zero to 11 (mean = 4.4 ± 2.8) and did not differ between three main habitat categories meadow, pasture or vineyard (ANOVA, $n=48$, $df=2$, $F=0.70$, $p=0.50$). To ensure breeding opportunities, we installed an additional 145 nest boxes around the experimental plots up to 200 m from the plot centers, resulting in a total number of nest boxes ranging from 1 to 36 (mean = 7.4 ± 5.8). Most of the nest boxes were commercially available Schwegler 3SV nest boxes with an entrance diameter of 34 mm. In the two occupied breeding areas at the western and eastern end of the study area, we selected another 22 plots as a reference (Knaus et al., 2018; Pauli, 2022), hereafter referred to as 'non-experimental breeding plots' (Figure 1). All plot centers were separated by at least 400 m to avoid non-independence. No permits were required for field work.

In June and July 2020, we collected land cover data of all experimental and non-experimental breeding plots and mapped the surface of the following 11 land use categories within each plot: meadows (intensively and extensively managed), pastures (intensively and extensively managed), vineyards (intensively and extensively managed), fallow land, crops, forest patches, hedges, and anthropogenic habitat (Coudrain et al., 2010; Weisshaupt et al., 2011). In addition, we retrieved temperature data (hourly means in °C) from the closest MeteoSwiss land-based weather station (MeteoSwiss, 2024) for each plot.

FIGURE 1 The study area along the southern foothills of the Jura mountains (Switzerland). Locations of the experimental plots in the central part (orange dots, no regular Wryneck breeding pairs) and the non-experimental breeding plots (yellow dots) at Lake Biel (western part, ca. 25 Wryneck breeding pairs) and Hallau (eastern part, ca. 20 Wryneck breeding pairs) are shown. The inset map shows the modelled range of the Wryneck in Switzerland with >0.1 territories per km^2 (Knaus et al., 2018). Background map © swisstopo.

2.3 | Playback experiment and field procedure

We used conspecific playback as a social cue on half of the plots in 2020 and 2021 (24 plots each with playback), whereas the other half without playback served as control (2020 and 2021: 24 plots each without playback). The treatment on each plot was switched between 2020 and 2021. Following a random stratified sampling, we distributed the playback evenly among the three main habitat categories (meadow, pasture or vineyard).

The playback devices, designed and built by the Swiss Ornithological Institute, played a male courtship song recorded in the study area (Lüthi, 2018) from mid-March until June in 2020 and 2021. The song is by far the most common Wryneck vocalization during this period, whereas calls and other vocalizations are rare. Since our goal was to mimic a territorial male, we only included the song of one individual in the recording. Playback took place 1, 3 and 5 h after sunrise, 1 h before sunset and once at 1 AM for 1 min each. The playback volume was adjusted to mimic natural conditions, making it audible up to ca. 100 m. We surveyed all 48 experimental plots between early April and June in 2020 and 2021. We visited every plot once a week during these periods (ca. eight visits per experimental

plot and year) and monitored Wrynecks as described by Coudrain et al. (2010) for approximately 30 min per visit. Ten minutes after the start of a visit, we broadcasted the same male courtship song used in the playback devices for 1 min with a mobile device and a portable Bluetooth speaker. After another 10 min, we played it a second time and waited another 10 min. Wrynecks react very strongly to conspecific songs, so playing their songs is a reliable method of assessing the presence of the species.

We have divided the time between arrival in the breeding area (mid-March) and the end of the breeding season (July) into two periods: the prospecting period and the breeding period. After returning to the breeding area from their wintering grounds, Wrynecks sing incessantly in search of potential mates, pair and inspect possible breeding cavities, usually accompanied by their mates (Glutz von Blotzheim, 1994; Pauli, 2022). This behaviour of the Wrynecks can be observed in our study area until mid-May, which is why we have defined the time upon arrival between arrival from the wintering ground until mid-May as the prospecting period. While unpaired Wrynecks can sing throughout spring and summer, paired Wrynecks significantly reduce their singing activity after laying their eggs (Glutz von Blotzheim, 1994; Pauli, 2022). Based on the breeding phenology

of Wrynecks from our study area (Pauli, 2022), we defined the time between mid-May and July as the breeding period.

We defined Wryneck occurrence on a plot separately for each study year (hereafter Wryneck occurrence, binary variable 0 or 1) when we detected at least one Wryneck on a plot during the prospecting or breeding periods. Similarly, we defined Wryneck prospecting on a plot separately for each study year (hereafter Wryneck prospecting, binary variable 0 or 1) when we detected at least one Wryneck on a plot during the prospecting period. Lastly, we defined breeding on a plot separately for each study year (hereafter Wryneck breeding, binary variable 0 or 1) when we detected evidence of breeding (e.g. occupation of a nest box or a natural breeding cavity, observation of courtship behaviour, feeding adults or fledglings) during the breeding period.

2.4 | Food availability and land use data

Data on food availability was collected on a random sample of all 48 experimental plots and 22 non-experimental breeding plots over 2 years (Table 1). Food availability on the experimental plots was sampled twice, the first time during the prospecting period of the Wryneck between mid-April and mid-May, and the second time during the breeding period from mid-May to mid-July. Food availability on the non-experimental breeding plots was sampled once during the breeding period between the end of May and mid-July.

We measured food availability at three hierarchical levels. Within each plot, we established four sampling locations, stratified according to the proportional cover of the main land use classes meadow, pasture, or vineyard. At each sampling location, we searched for ants in five 2m² replicates. During a 7-min survey, we searched on the surface of each of the five replicates for anthills and then scraped the soil with a small rake to a depth of 3 cm for underground nests to detect the presence of ants and count the number of ant nests. In addition, we recorded habitat variables with a known effect on ant habitat selection and accessibility (Mermod et al., 2009; Seifert, 2018): habitat type (intensively and extensively managed meadow, intensively and extensively managed pasture, intensively and extensively managed vineyards), vegetation height (in cm), and the proportion of bare ground (in %).

TABLE 1 Overview of the number of all plots and their sampling regime, sampling locations and replicates sampled for food availability. Plots were sampled once (either only in the prospecting period or only in the breeding period) or twice (in the prospecting and the breeding period).

	Year	Plots	Plots sampled	Prospecting only	Breeding only	Prospecting and breeding	Sampling locations (replicates)
Non-experimental breeding plots	2020	22	18	0	18	0	72 (359)
Experimental plots		48	36	6	1	29	134 (1238)
Total		70	54	6	19	29	206 (1597)
Non-experimental breeding plots	2021	22	17	0	17	0	68 (339)
Experimental plots		48	46	17	0	29	178 (1414)
Total		70	63	17	17	29	246 (1753)

Food availability (i.e. ant nest density) was collected for 36 out of 48 experimental plots in 2020, with 29 plots sampled twice (once during the prospecting period and once during the breeding period) and seven plots sampled only once (six only in prospecting period and one only in the breeding period). In 2021, we collected food availability for 46 out of 48 experimental plots in 2021, with 29 plots sampled twice (both periods) and 17 plots sampled once (all in the prospecting period). Likewise, food availability was sampled once in 18 out of 22 non-experimental breeding plots in 2020 and in 17 out of 22 non-experimental breeding plots in 2021 (all in the breeding period). The sample size of the sampling points and replicates (Table 1) did not always reach the maximum number of sampling points (number of sampled plots × 4) and replicates (number of sampling locations × 5) because certain sampling locations and/or replicates were not carried out due to inaccessibility (e.g. free-ranging livestock) or a change in land use during the study (e.g. ploughing).

2.5 | Statistical analysis

Models were performed in R Studio version 4.4.1, implemented in a Bayesian framework with the 'rstanarm' package version 2.32.1 (Goodrich et al., 2022). Continuous variables were standardized before the analysis. First, we modelled food availability for the Wrynecks by predicting ant nest density per habitat type using Poisson GLMMs fitted with a log-link function in rstanarm (Goodrich et al., 2022). We analysed the effects of habitat type (categorical variable with six levels: intensively and extensively managed meadow, intensively and extensively managed pasture, intensively and extensively managed vineyards), year (categorical variable with two levels: 2020 and 2021), sampling period (categorical variable with two levels: prospecting period and breeding period) and temperature (continuous variable) on the abundance of ant groups using the data from all sampled experimental and non-experimental breeding plots (Table 1, Table S1). The sampling location was included as a random factor to account for repeated sampling over 2 years and two sampling periods per year. Temperature was included to account for ant detection probability (Mermod et al., 2009). Predicted ant nest abundance per m² and habitat type were then multiplied by

the respective amount of habitat on each plot to obtain a proxy for total food availability on each plot.

Subsequently, we performed three different analyses using binomial GLMMs fitted with a logit-link function to assess Wryneck occurrence, prospecting and breeding. First, we modelled Wryneck habitat suitability in our study area (habitat suitability model; across all sampled experimental and non-experimental breeding plots during both study years) and fitted Wryneck occurrence as a dependent binary variable and the predicted food availability, bare ground, year and sampling period as explanatory variables. We then additionally tested for differences in Wryneck occurrence by including a categorical variable with two levels: experimental and non-experimental plots. Second, we investigated the factors affecting Wryneck prospecting on the experimental plots (playback experiment model—prospecting). For this purpose, we fitted Wryneck prospecting from the sampled experimental plots as a dependent binary variable and playback, food availability and their interaction, as well as bare ground and year as explanatory variables. Third, we determined the factors affecting Wryneck breeding on the experimental plots (playback experiment model—breeding). Thus, we fitted Wryneck breeding from the sampled experimental plots as a dependent variable and—as in the second model—playback, food availability and their interaction, as well as bare ground and year as explanatory variables. All models were run with 10,000 iterations (four chains of 5000 iterations with a burn-in of 2500 each).

All explanatory variables were retained in the models, because none of them showed a correlation of Pearson's $r \geq 0.7$. All continuous explanatory variables were centered and scaled. We ensured that effective sample sizes were above 1000 and Rhat smaller than 1.1 (Gelman & Rubin, 1992). Models were checked for convergence with Brooks-Rubin-Gelman diagnostics (Brooks & Gelman, 1998) and for validity using posterior predictive checks (package 'shinystan'; Gabry, 2018). Spatial autocorrelation in the residuals was checked using Moran's I and bubbleplots (package 'DHARMA'; Hartig, 2022) and no remaining autocorrelation was detected (p -values > 0.05 , for all Moran's I tests). Models were created based on ecological hypotheses and non-informative interactions were

removed, but no model selection on the fixed effects was performed (Korner-Nievergelt et al., 2015). Inference and predictions were based on Bayesian posterior distributions. We obtained estimated marginal means for post hoc comparisons using the package 'emmeans' (Lenth, 2017). Additionally, posterior probabilities (PP) were calculated for all model estimates, indicating the probability of the estimates to differ from zero. Estimates were considered to have a strong effect if $PP \geq 0.95$ and a weak effect if $0.95 > PP > 0.9$. Unless stated otherwise, model parameters and derived parameters are given as posterior means with 95% credible intervals (CrI).

3 | RESULTS

Food availability, that is, ant nest density, was measured at three hierarchical levels (replicates, sampling locations with 5 replicates, and plots with 4 sampling locations). The raw values varied between 0 and 6 nests in replicates (mean = 0.84 ± 0.98 nests, $n = 3283$ replicates), between 0 and 17 nests in sampling locations (mean = 4.06 ± 2.91 nests, $n = 564$ sampling locations), and between 1 and 38 nests in plots (mean = 15.26 ± 7.96 nests, $n = 91$ plots). Food availability measured as ant nests per m^2 resulted in 0 to 1.7 nests per m^2 (mean = 0.39 ± 0.29 nests) and clearly differed among habitat types (Table 2, Table S1). Food availability was highest in vineyards—regardless of their management—followed by extensively managed meadows and pastures, and lowest in intensively managed meadows and pastures (Figure 2, Table S1). Extrapolated food availability per plot ranged from 2838 to 24,589 ant nests (mean = $12,966 \pm 4752$ ant nests) and was higher (two-sided t -test, $t = -7.91$, $p < 0.001$) on non-experimental breeding plots occupied by Wrynecks (mean = $17,406 \pm 4361$, min = 11,411, max = 24,589 ant nests) than on experimental plots (mean = $11,857 \pm 3529$, min = 2838, max = 22,934 ant nests). Food availability strongly increased with temperature and was consistently higher in the second sampling period than in the first sampling period, while it did not vary between years (Table S1). The proportion of bare ground at the sampling locations was on average 12.2% and varied between 5.0% and 27.5% (Table 2).

TABLE 2 Mean, standard deviation (SD), minimum (min) and maximum (max) of raw data values of food availability and bare ground per habitat type. Sample size is the yearly number of samples taken at the sampling locations.

Habitat type	Food availability [ant nest density per m^2]				Bare ground [proportion of the area at the sampling locations in %]				Sample size		
	Mean	SD	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Min	Max	2020	2021	Total
Vineyard extensively managed	0.48	0.27	0	1.7	15.6	5.4	7.1	26.6	61	61	122
Vineyard intensively managed	0.57	0.35	0	1.5	15.6	6.5	7.1	21.7	53	55	108
Meadow extensively managed	0.38	0.26	0	1.1	9.9	3.8	5.0	22.6	57	75	132
Meadow intensively managed	0.24	0.20	0	0.7	8.8	2.7	5.0	13.6	32	34	66
Pasture extensively managed	0.33	0.27	0	1.2	12.5	4.1	5.0	18.3	112	123	235
Pasture intensively managed	0.17	0.15	0	0.4	12.6	5.4	5.5	27.5	6	8	14
Total	0.39	0.29	0	1.7	12.2	5.1	5.0	27.5	321	356	677

3.1 | Habitat suitability model

The probability of Wryneck occurrence on all sampled plots was strongly positively related to food availability and increased from

FIGURE 2 Predicted food availability, that is, ant nest density per m² (mean values and 95% credible intervals), on all experimental and non-experimental breeding plots averaged over both years for different habitat types and sampling periods.

TABLE 3 Parameter estimates of the habitat suitability model, the playback experiment model—prospecting, and the playback experiment model—breeding; data were obtained on 54 plots in 2020 and 63 plots in 2021.

Model	Parameter	Posterior mean	95% CrI	PP
Habitat suitability	Intercept	-1.49	-2.61 to -0.45	
	Food availability	0.77	-0.08 to 1.78	0.96
	Bare ground	0.55	-0.23 to 1.41	0.92
	Year	0.20	-0.66 to 1.09	0.68
	Sampling period	0.40	-0.81 to 1.54	0.74
	Random effect (plot identity)	3.51	0.95 to 10.38	
Playback experiment—prospecting	Intercept	-1.99	-3.66 to -0.66	
	Food availability	1.99	0.24 to 4.03	0.99
	Playback	0.38	-1.06 to 1.82	0.69
	Food availability × playback	-2.29	-4.49 to -0.37	0.99
	Bare ground	0.12	-0.72 to 0.95	0.62
	Year	0.31	-1.03 to 1.70	0.66
	Random effect (plot identity)	0.62	0.00 to 6.49	
Playback experiment—breeding	Intercept	-4.98	-8.39 to -2.38	
	Food availability	1.46	-0.26 to 3.29	0.95
	Playback	-2.05	-5.07 to 0.52	0.94
	Bare ground	0.06	-1.60 to 1.64	0.46
	Year	2.24	-0.47 to 5.39	0.95
	Random effect (plot identity)	1.62	0.00 to 14.48	

Note: 95% CrI=95% credibility intervals of posterior means; posterior probabilities (PP) were calculated for all model estimates, indicating the probability of the estimates to differ from zero. Variables with PP values larger than 0.9 are highlighted in bold.

0.04 (95% CrI=0.00–0.22) at minimal ant densities to 0.60 (95% CrI=0.11–0.96) at maximal ant densities (Table 3, Figure 3). It was 3.41 times higher (95% CrI=1.36–5.44) on non-experimental plots than on experimental plots. In addition, Wryneck occurrence increased weakly with the proportion of bare ground, but did not differ between sampling periods and years (Table 3).

3.2 | Playback experiment model—Prospecting

During the 2 years of the playback experiment, we detected Wrynecks prospecting on 19 of the 48 previously unoccupied experimental plots (12 plots with playback, 7 plots without playback). We found a strong interactive effect between playback and food availability on Wryneck prospecting (Table 3, Figure 4a). In control plots without playback, the probability of Wryneck prospecting increased with food availability. Experimental playback increased Wryneck prospecting in plots of low food availability, but not in plots of high food availability (Figure 4a).

3.3 | Playback experiment model—Breeding

Only a small number of Wrynecks prospecting on the 48 previously unoccupied playback experiment plots settled and started breeding. In 2020, one pair successfully raised two consecutive broods on a plot without playback, while no broods were detected on plots

FIGURE 3 Wryneck occurrence probability (habitat suitability model) in relation to ant nest density per m^2 . Predicted means (blue line) and 95% credible intervals (light blue shadings) are shown, with predictions for the year 2020, the first sampling period, and the mean value of bare ground. The black points represent the raw Wryneck occurrence data from 54 (in 2020) and 63 (in 2021) experimental and non-experimental breeding plots during two sampling periods (Table 1).

with playback. In 2021, three pairs started breeding on experimental plots (two pairs on plots with playback; one pair on a plot without playback), but only one of the broods on a plot with playback was successful. After excluding the unsupported interaction between playback and food availability (95% CrI: -2.63 to 3.41 , $PP=0.44$), food availability had a positive effect on Wryneck breeding, as well as the factor 'year' (higher breeding probability in 2021), while playback had a negative effect (Table 3). High food availability increased the probability of Wryneck breeding in all experimental plots, while playback reduced the probability of Wryneck breeding. As no Wrynecks bred in plots with low ant nest densities, the difference between the playback and the control group without playback was only evident at very high ant nest densities (Figure 4b).

4 | DISCUSSION

Social information can influence habitat selection and trigger the settlement in birds (Betts et al., 2008; Ward & Schlossberg, 2004). Therefore, experimental social cues to attract individuals have been widely tested and applied for conservation management (Ahlering et al., 2010; Valente et al., 2021). Nevertheless, little is known about the relative importance of social versus personal information for different stages of habitat selection in birds so far (but see Rushing et al., 2021; Swift et al., 2023). Here, we found clear evidence for the importance of personal information in terms of food availability at two different stages of the settlement process of Wrynecks. Wrynecks clearly preferred plots with high ant nest densities during prospecting

FIGURE 4 Wryneck prospecting probability (a) and Wryneck breeding probability (b) in relation to ant nest density per m^2 in non-playback plots (black) and playback plots (blue). Predicted means (lines) and 95% credible intervals (shadings) are shown, with predictions for the year 2020, the first sampling period, and the mean value of bare ground. The points represent (a) the raw Wryneck prospecting data from all sampled experimental plots in 2020 and 2021 during the prospecting period ($n=81$, Table 1) and (b) the raw Wryneck breeding data from all sampled experimental plots in 2020 and 2021 during the settlement and breeding period ($n=59$, Table 1).

and for breeding. Yet, social information in terms of conspecific vocalization increased the probability of prospecting before settlement in low-quality but not high-quality habitat patches but decreased the probability of settling and breeding. These results suggest that Wrynecks rely on a combination of social and personal cues to find potential breeding sites but use mainly personal information about habitat quality for settlement decisions. Hence, Wrynecks can be attracted to potential breeding sites by playback, but they will not settle if food availability is restricted. The low Wryneck population density and therefore limited mate availability in our study area may have contributed to the low settlement (Kokko & Rankin, 2006). Importantly, our experiment also shows that the use of playback as an attraction method does not result in an ecological trap in Wrynecks.

4.1 | Habitat effects—Food availability

Wryneck occurrence, measured over the annual period when Wrynecks are present in the study area, was predominantly related to food availability and to the proportion of bare ground. High food availability (i.e. ant nest density) and food accessibility (i.e. the proportion of bare ground) are thus likely key features for habitat quality of the Wryneck.

Our experiment confirmed the positive effect of increased food availability on prospecting and breeding probability. In addition, Wryneck occurrence was more likely on plots with a lot of bare ground. Food availability and accessibility are therefore confirmed to be of paramount importance for Wryneck conservation (Coudrain et al., 2010; Freitag, 1998; Mermod et al., 2009; Schaub et al., 2010; Weisshaupt et al., 2011). However, the experimental study failed to show an effect on prospecting and breeding probability, most likely due to the limited sample size. The results suggest that returning Wrynecks avoid using sites with suitable breeding cavities, such as tree holes and nest boxes, if they do not provide high food resources. We therefore recommend that nest boxes for Wrynecks be provided only at sites with high food availability (>0.3 ant nests per m^2), with the aim of maximizing the effect of conservation efforts. In our study area, this applies particularly to vineyards and extensively managed meadows. As volunteers from local nature conservation organizations frequently undertake this work, the presumably higher success rate of this measure would also serve to increase their motivation and reinforce their commitment (Phillips et al., 2019).

The ant nest densities obtained in our study are largely consistent with those reported by Coudrain et al. (2010) and Mermod et al. (2009). However, our values were generally smaller, particularly in vineyards and meadows. This discrepancy might be at least partially attributable to the less favourable climatic conditions for the mainly xerothermophilic ants in our study area. Acquiring knowledge about ant densities can be time consuming for researchers and conservationists. Quantifying ant nest density took us about half a day per plot. Nevertheless, we show here that the nest density of ground-dwelling ants can be determined in the field without the need for species identification and that quantifying ant nest density serves as an effective predictor of Wryneck occurrence. We therefore recommend our user-friendly method of quantifying ant nest density for estimating food availability not only for the Wryneck, but also for other ground-dwelling ant-feeding species such as the Grey-headed Woodpecker *Picus canus* or the European Green Woodpecker *Picus viridis*.

4.2 | Habitat effects—Agricultural management

Food availability was highest in vineyards in our study area, probably because ants profit from small-scale management offering a temporally and spatially diverse mosaic of habitat patches with a substantial proportion of bare ground (Seifert, 2018). Vineyards were followed by extensively managed grasslands (meadows and

pastures), where the use of fertilizers is largely restricted. These results are in line with the fact that ant nest abundance, as well as ant species richness and abundance, increase with low intensity of land use (Heuss et al., 2019). However, the direct influence of fertilisation on ant species richness remains unclear, despite negative indirect effects through the alteration of plant communities (Dahms et al., 2005; Scharnhorst et al., 2021).

To increase habitat quality in terms of food availability for Wrynecks, we recommend ant-friendly agricultural management actions such as reducing land use intensity and nutrient-reducing field treatment, for example alternating vegetating of vineyard rows (Bosco et al., 2019; Brambilla & Gatti, 2022), grazing rotation, or mowing regimes, resulting in a mosaic of different field structures in pastures and meadows (Fuhlendorf et al., 2006; Hübner et al., 2004; Wübbenhorst, 2012). We particularly recommend creating extensive grassland strips with the aim of increasing or maintaining high habitat suitability for ants, especially at existing or potential breeding sites with breeding cavities or nest boxes (Scharnhorst et al., 2021). Ant-friendly management in combination with the promotion of a highly structured landscape (e.g. hedges, single trees and fallow land) also supports other regionally endangered species such as the Woodlark *Lullula arborea*, Cirl Bunting *Emberiza cirlus*, Hoopoe *Upupa epops*, Common Redstart *Phoenicurus phoenicurus*, Red-backed Shrike *Lanius collurio*, and Common Linnet *Linaria cannabina*, as well as overall bird diversity (Barbaro et al., 2021; Guyot et al., 2017; Tschumi et al., 2020).

4.3 | Playback effects

Playback had a positive effect on Wryneck prospecting probability, but only in habitats with low food availability. Thus, the relationship between Wryneck prospecting and food availability disappeared with playback (Figure 4a). Subsequently, playback had a negative effect on breeding probability, prevalent only in habitats with high food availability. We attribute this negative effect of playback to the random variation of outcomes in studies with small sample sizes as we observed breeding only in three high-quality habitat plots (out of total of four plots with breeding). Furthermore, it is difficult to explain why playback-attracted birds should settle less than non-attracted birds in plots of the same habitat quality. An alternative explanation would be that unevenly distributed other factors lead to this outcome.

Our results imply that playback did not create an ecological trap (Hale & Swearer, 2016). Although prospecting was enhanced in sites with low food availability, Wrynecks did not settle or breed there. The breeding success in all broods on experimental plots was relatively high (3 of 4 broods with fledged young) and the number of fledglings in successful broods (mean = 7, range: 6 to 8) was comparable to that reported under natural conditions of Wryneck populations in Central Europe (Glutz von Blotzheim, 1994; Pauli, 2022; Tenan et al., 2021). Furthermore, two breeding pairs also successfully raised a second brood, which is seen in only 20%–34% of

breeding pairs, indicating good breeding conditions (Pauli, 2022; Tolkmitt et al., 2009). Based on this supplementary evaluation of breeding success, which is a crucial element in the context of conservation, we are confident that playback does not exert a significant detrimental effect on the breeding success of the attracted individuals. Nevertheless, the use of playback must be applied with caution. Playback may retain individuals in low-quality habitats and delay arrival at sites that are more suitable for breeding and drain valuable energy resources (Stamps, 2001), thereby reducing the chance of successful reproduction. Thus, the application of playback as a conservation measure must avoid attracting birds to habitats of low quality.

Even though we could not show a positive effect of playback on breeding probability in high-quality habitats, we suggest that experimental playback may serve as a cost-effective tool to attract Wrynecks to sites of conservation efforts without having negative impacts. Playback thereby could support colonization of high-quality sites (Lewis et al., 2021), particularly in areas far from existing breeding pairs. It can therefore be used selectively under certain conditions and only in consultation with specialist advisors as a management tool for conservation strategies (such as in Switzerland). We also propose further research to test Wryneck colonization of unoccupied, high-quality habitat patches in areas of both low and high conspecific densities in an existing population network using playback experiments. Careful selection of playback recordings is important, also to avoid potential methodological problems (e.g. pseudoreplication, see Kroodsma, 1989; Kroodsma et al., 2001). We might suppose that playback can accelerate the growth of existing populations in areas with unoccupied sites of high food availability, given that Wryneck population dynamics correlated more strongly with immigration than with reproduction and survival rates (Schaub et al., 2012; Tenan et al., 2021).

4.4 | Personal versus social information in Wryneck habitat selection

Both directly acquired personal information and indirect social information influenced habitat selection in Wrynecks. Our experiment provides evidence that personal information about the available food resources had a greater influence on breeding habitat selection, while social information from conspecific vocalizations increased the occurrence probability of prospecting Wrynecks only in habitats with poor food availability. Since food availability in the breeding season can regulate reproduction and limit population size (Arcese & Smith, 1988), direct information about available resources is likely to provide more important information about habitat quality and breeding success than the information indirectly provided by conspecifics. Wrynecks may perceive high food availability as an important habitat cue and prospect and use such high-quality habitats irrespective of the presence of conspecifics. Social information can thus be used as a complementary or alternative source of

information when personal information is unavailable or insufficient. Indeed, social cues may provide information about where to stop migrating and start prospecting habitats, which is evaluated by obtaining direct personal information. In summary, our results suggest that while Wrynecks use social information for prospecting, they use personal information from assessing food resources, rather than social cues, for their final settlement decision.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Matthias Vögeli, Martin U. Grübler, Michael Lanz, Martin Schuck and Reto Spaar conceived the ideas and designed the methodology; Paula Schatte, Michael Lanz and Matthias Vögeli collected the data; Paula Schatte, Matthias Tschumi and Matthias Vögeli analysed the data; Paula Schatte and Matthias Vögeli led the writing of the manuscript with substantial support from Matthias Tschumi and Martin U. Grübler. All authors contributed critically to the drafts and gave final approval for publication.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

PEER REVIEW

The peer review history for this article is available at <https://www.webofscience.com/api/gateway/wos/peer-review/10.1002/2688-8319.70041>.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data and code are available on the vogelwarte.ch Open Repository and Archive: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15189559> (Schatte et al., 2025).

STATEMENT ON INCLUSION

Our study brings together different authors, including scientists (P.S., M.U.G., M.T. and M.V.) and practitioners (M.L., M.S. and R.S.) based in the country where we conducted the study. The first

author of our study was a master's student supervised by the last author. All authors were engaged early on with the research and study design to ensure that the diverse sets of perspectives they represent were considered from the onset. Whenever relevant, we cited literature published by scientists from Central Europe and in particular the country where we conducted the study. We made efforts to consider relevant work, also grey literature, published in the local languages.

RELEVANT GREY LITERATURE

You can find related grey literature on the topics below on Applied Ecology Resources: [Conservation management](#), [habitat selection](#), [social information](#).

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Table S1. Parameter estimates of a GLMM investigating factors affecting food availability (i.e. ant nest density per m²). 95% CrI=95% credibility intervals of posterior means; posterior probabilities (PP) were calculated for all model estimates, indicating the probability of the estimates to differ from zero. Variables with PP-values larger than 0.9 are highlighted in bold.

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